

Tobit Regression Analysis of Factors Influencing Market Access on the Harvesting Yield of Long Coriander in Battambang, Cambodia

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Abstract

Long Coriander, a highly valued leafy vegetable in Southeast Asia, is related to the coriander family. It enhances the flavor of common ingredients in Central and Southeast Asian cuisine and has a distinct coriander scent. Due to its strong market demand and recognized health benefits, it holds significant potential for small-scale producers in the Battambang region of Cambodia. To accomplish this research's objectives, this study delves into the statistical significance of market access on harvesting yield, employing Tobit and stepwise regression analyses to identify key factors influencing the quantity of Long Coriander harvested by Battambang producers. By analyzing censored data, researchers aim to uncover the challenges faced by these producers in accessing markets and their impact on yield. The findings will inform targeted interventions to enhance market opportunities, discover effective development strategies for the economic sustainability of Long Coriander crop, improve producer livelihoods, and optimize production outcomes. Additionally, this research contributes to a deeper understanding of agricultural production factors in the region and provides a foundation for future studies on Long Coriander cultivation.

Keywords: *Tobit Regression, Factors Influencing, Market Access, Harvesting Yield, Long Coriander, Chi Rona, Cambodia.*

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Introduction

Long Coriander, widely recognized for its distinctive taste, is considered an essential ingredient in Cambodian cuisine. Based on the farmers, this is called *Chi Rona* in Khmer, also known as *Chi Banla*, *Chi Baraing*, or *Chi Pa-la* (Darith et al., 2024b; Sophath, 2010). Alternatively, in other countries, Long Coriander is also known by a few different names, including "Puerto Rican coriander, Black Benny, Saw leaf herb, Mexican coriander, Saw tooth coriander, Spiny coriander, Fitweed" (Sophath, 2010). The Caribbean Islands are considered the original birthplace of this plant. Currently, it is being introduced to many regions of Southeast Asia, including Indonesia, Malaysia, and Indochina (Sokunthea et al., 2023; Eryngium, 2024). Coriander is classified as a plant, specifically belonging to the *Plantae kingdom*. Within this kingdom, the Long Coriander is categorized under the family of *Apiaceae*, and the specific genus is *E. foetidum*. Consequently, combining the genus and species gives us the binomial name *Eryngium foetidum* (Sophath, 2010). While Long Coriander looks different from other types of coriander, its long, tough stems have a similar smell. This similarity suggests that Long Coriander could be a potential substitute for regular coriander (Katzner, 2024). Interestingly, despite originating in Asia, Long Coriander quickly became a popular alternative to Mediterranean remedies in the region. Although previously unknown, Long Coriander has also gained popularity as a houseplant during the summer (Sovannarith, 2009).

Long Coriander, a popular leafy vegetable that is commonly eaten, recently known as a popular leafy vegetable green with fragrant long leaves, can now be easily grown at home (Figure 1). Seeds are widely available from various sources, including seed suppliers, Asian and Latin markets, and online retailers (Sokunthea et al., 2023). The plant has long, fibrous roots and evergreen stems that grow to a height of 15 to 20 cm. The leaves appear rosette-patterned with long, serrated margins (Eryngium, 2024; Mann, 2023). The cylindrical blossoms of the Long Coriander plant have rounded apices and measure approximately 1.2 cm in length and 0.5 cm in width. In Southeast Asia, this plant produces flowers throughout the year.

Long Coriander fruits are tiny, oval-shaped, about 1.5 millimeters in length, and covered in small spheres (Mann, 2023). In the basic cultivation process of Long Coriander, farmers traditionally sow seeds directly onto the ground for 1,600 square meters in a plot and use between 3 to 5 kg of seeds. Before planting, soaking the seeds for two days is recommended. Then, farmers simply combine 6 tablespoons of seeds with a certain amount of ashes once the seeds have soaked. The surface of the prepared soil is then directly scattered with the mixture. 15 days after sowing, the soil must be well watered to allow for seed germination (Sokhom, 2004; Sokunthea et al., 2023).

In addition to its exceptional flavor, Long Coriander is an important ingredient in many dishes. It is mostly used in Southeast Asia and Central America; in Thailand, Malaysia, and Singapore, it is a common topping for soups, noodles, and curries, frequently taking the place of regular coriander. Thai curry pastes also often use Long Coriander, as coriander roots are not available in those regions. Although fresh herbs are generally emphasized in Vietnamese cuisine, Long Coriander also has a place there (Ramcharan, 1999; Sophath, 2010).

Figure 1. Harvest of Long Coriander
Source: Authors, 2024

Aside from being an important ingredient in many kinds of dishes, Long Coriander is highly valued in South American countries like Peru, Colombia, and Ecuador for its medicinal properties. Traditionally used to alleviate digestive discomfort such as bloating, diarrhea, and an upset stomach, this plant is also believed to support women's health. Research suggests it may help regulate menstrual cycles, reduce menstrual cramps, boost fertility, aid childbirth, and even enhance sexual desire (Flora et al., 2023; Mann, 2023; Sokunthea et al., 2023). Also, the potential health benefits of Long Coriander have been highlighted by scientific studies. This tasty plant is a great source of many nutrients besides being a taste delight. It contains a high content of antioxidants, carotenoids, phytosterols, vitamins, and minerals. Fresh Long Coriander leaves are comprised of 87% moisture, 6.5% carbohydrates, 3.3% protein, 0.6% fat, 1.7% ash, 0.06% phosphorus, and 0.02% iron. Additionally, Long Coriander is a significant source of vitamins, containing 10,460 IU of vitamin A, 60 mg of vitamin B2, 0.8 mg of vitamin B1, and 150–200 mg of vitamin C per 100 grams (Bautista et al., 1988; Flora et al., 2023; Ramcharan, 1999; Sophath, 2010).

Long Coriander seeds are a profitable crop for Cambodian producers. The market price for the seeds typically ranges from 100,000 riels (approx. \$24.29) to 90,000 riels (approx. \$21.86) per kilogram per kg. However, the price of Long Coriander crop always fluctuates, just like the others in the market. Producers pay the lowest price, between 1,500 and 2,500 riels (approx. \$0.36 to \$0.61) per kg, while market sellers start at 3,500 to 4,000 riels (approx. \$0.85 to \$0.97). During the off-season, Long Coriander crop prices for producers selling to brokers range from 3,500 to 5,000 riels (approx. \$0.85 to \$1.21), while market sellers offer them between 7,000 and 9,000 riels (approx. \$1.70 to \$2.19) per kg (according to the producers, 2024). The high profit margins make Long Coriander cultivation an attractive agricultural venture in Cambodia (Eav & Darith, 2024; Sokunthea et al., 2023).

Sustainable farming is an integrated approach to agriculture that balances environmental, economic, and social considerations. It aims to produce food in a way that is both profitable and environmentally responsible, considering the farm's natural resources, the farmer's financial needs, and their family circumstances. According to Ma & Rahut (2024), and Pretty (2008), sustainable agriculture involves producing crops and livestock abundantly while minimizing harm to the planet and pollution. This study examines the integration, commercial viability, and production challenges of Long Coriander crop in Battambang, Cambodia. Beyond its potential as a leafy green, the research also investigates market accessibility and economic incentives for cultivating this crop. By using Tobit and stepwise regression analyses to identify key factors that significantly influence harvesting yield, the study aims to provide valuable insights that can help producers optimize their cultivation practices, overcome obstacles, and increase harvesting yield. Additionally, the research contributes to the broader knowledge base on crop production.

Methodology

Data Sources and Descriptions

The descriptive statistics of inputs for Long Coriander function-value analysis (**Table 1**) is paramount for optimizing production yield and maximizing producers' income. Key inputs such as cultivated land (*cul_area*), seed rate (*cul_Seed*), total land (*total_land*), number of plants per year (*YN_plantYear*), and number of harvests per year (*Y_Harvest_year*) are all significantly correlated with Long Coriander yield. The average cultivated land used is 1.24 Rai, with seed rates averaging 3.96 kg per Rai. Total land averages 7.14 Rai, with producers cultivating an average of 2.66 plants per year and harvesting 5.46 times per year. In addition, understanding the relationship between these variables and the resulting yield (*Y_harvest*) could provide valuable insights for optimizing Long Coriander production and help in developing targeted income yield.

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics of Inputs for Long Coriander Production Function-Value Analysis

Variable	Definition	Obs.	Mean	Group	Obs.	Y_harvest	SD
<i>cul_area</i>	Cultivated Land (Rai)	50	1.24	> 1.24	13	1180.77	323.74
				≤ 1.24	37	1133.78	367.81
<i>cul_Seed</i>	Seed Rate Per Rai (Kg)	50	3.96	> 3.96	27	1125.93	393.06
				≤ 3.96	23	1169.57	309.60
<i>total_land</i>	Total of Land (Rai)	50	7.14	> 7.14	11	1063.64	375.56
				≤ 7.14	39	1169.23	349.55
<i>Y_N_plantYear</i>	Number of Plants Per Year	50	2.66	> 2.66	25	1100.00	254.95
				≤ 2.66	25	1192.00	432.21
<i>Y_Harvest_year</i>	Number of Harvests Per Year	50	5.46	> 5.46	28	1235.71	387.26
				≤ 5.46	22	1031.82	274.97

Descriptive statistics were used in the regression study to determine the inputs for Long Coriander production cost-value analysis for harvesting yield. These statistics helped understand the characteristics of the information that considers various cost variables impacting the harvesting yield of Long Coriander production. The information in Table 2 outlines key variables, definitions, and associated statistical

measures. Initially, variables include input factors cost of seeds (*material_7*), cost of energy resource and water pump/engine (*Material_energyEngin*), cost of chemical fertilizer and biocide (herbicide) (*Material_cheFerti*), cost of other materials (*Material_Other Cost*), labor for excavation, plowing, and harvesting (*Labor_1-3*) as well as cost of transportation (*Exp_2*). Additionally, the output factor, price per riel (kg), represented as "*Y_price*," is also included. For each variable, the table presented the mean values, the number of observations, and the yield (*Y_harvest*) categorized into groups based on specific thresholds. The information gathered undoubtedly served as a basis for income yield analysis and the identification of logical variables influencing the market access on the harvesting yield of Long Coriander production in the particular region.

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics of Inputs for Long Coriander Production Cost-Value Analysis

Variable	Definition	Obs.	Mean (*1000)	Group (*1000)	Obs.	Y_harvest (*1000)	SD
<i>material_7</i>	Cost of Seed	50	598.00	> 598.00	18	1.0806	328.61
				≤ 598.00	32	1.1828	367.78
<i>Material_energyEngin</i>	Cost of Energy Resource & Water Pump/Engine	50	635.29	> 635.29	19	1.1105	316.48
				≤ 635.29	31	1.1677	378.93
<i>Material_cheFerti</i>	Cost of Chemical Fertilizer & Biocide (Herbicide)	50	392.12	> 392.12	14	1.2321	386.11
				≤ 392.12	36	1.1125	340.88
<i>Material_Other Cost</i>	Cost of Other Materials (1-6)	50	5974.8	> 5974.84	20	1.1375	319.90
				≤ 5974.84	30	1.1517	380.67
<i>Exp_2</i>	Cost of Transportation	50	4.95	> 4.95	10	1.2800	407.70
				≤ 4.95	40	1.1125	336.98
<i>Labor_1</i>	Labor of Excavation	50	74.79	> 74.79	15	1.2200	396.77
				≤ 74.79	35	1.1143	335.54
<i>Labor_2</i>	Labor of Plowing	50	168.54	> 168.54	14	1.0607	312.67
				≤ 168.54	36	1.1792	367.88
<i>labor_3</i>	Labor of Harvesting	50	946.60	> 946.60	19	1.1763	342.53
				≤ 946.60	31	1.1274	365.57
<i>Y_price</i>	Price Per Riel (Kg)	50	3.42	> 3.42	41	1.1768	365.39
				≤ 3.42	9	1.0056	272.08

Data Collection

The research was carried out in the Tonle Sap Lake region of northwest Cambodia, in the province of Battambang. Vast areas of farmland in this region are well-known for producing large quantities of rice and other grains. The most important supply of food for Cambodian farmers is agricultural products. This third-largest city in Cambodia has a total population of 987,400 (Chhay, 2019; Darith et al., 2024c). Also, Cambodia is a Southeast Asian country positioned at the southern tip of the Indochina Peninsula. Its climate is characterized by a tropical monsoon (Darith et al., 2024a; Suepa et al., 2016), with a distinct wet season spanning from May to October and a dry season extending from November to April. Notably, the Mekong River traverses Cambodia's flat lowlands, and Tonle Sap Lake is encircled by elevated plateaus and cultivated slopes monsoon (Burnett et al., 2017; Darith et al., 2016; Siek et al., 2024).

The data for this research was collected by quantitative methods. Interviews were conducted with approximately 50 households in the province of Battambang, Cambodia. Information from six villages was collected using the structured questionnaire, as indicated in **Table 3**. The non-random purposive sampling method was also used in the research, with the primary focus on farmers who cultivate the crop called Long Coriander. This study investigated the factors influencing market access on the harvesting yield of Long Coriander production. Tobit regression analysis was the primary model used in this study, while stepwise regression analysis was employed as a secondary model to clarify the significance levels of each influence factor.

According to Tobin (1958), Tobit regression, the statistical model designed for handling censored data, was introduced by renowned economist James Tobin in his groundbreaking 1958 *Econometrica* paper, "Estimation of Relationships for Limited Dependent Variables." This model was specifically developed to address the complexities arising from data where the variable of interest is restricted to a certain range and values outside this range are not fully observable.

Direct observation was conducted on-site to assess the general conditions, demographics, and farming systems of the area. By examining living circumstances and current Long Coriander cultivation, researchers determined local agricultural practices and compared planting variations among different villages.

Key informant meetings Interviews were conducted with local authorities, including district chiefs, commune chiefs, and village heads. These meetings aimed to gather general topics about the materials used, the total land used for Long Coriander cultivation, connections with middlemen, and market demand and price.

Table 3. Selected Site and Sampling Method

Province	District	Commune	Village	Household Population	<i>Purposive sample selection in Non-Random Sampling</i>	
					Sample size	% of Sample size
Battambang	Thma Koul	Ta Meun	Samraong	245	11	22
			Ta Sei	694	8	16
			Ang Cheung	412	6	12
			Krasang	352	10	20
		Ta Pung	Tumpung Tboung	448	6	12
			Ang Tboung	441	9	18
1 Province	1 District	2 Communes	6 Villages	2592	50	100

Survey-structured questionnaires were used to conduct in-depth interviews with farmers who planted the Long Coriander crop. These interviews covered various aspects of labor and land preparation, including organic fertilizer, seed, chemical fertilizer, energy resources, transportation costs, and labor costs (excavation, plowing, and harvesting). The additional study, based on the analysis, focused on examining the statistical significance of each variable affecting market access and their influence on Long Coriander harvest yield.

Model and Data Analysis

The study used statistical software called STATA to examine the key factors affecting market access and their influence on Long Coriander harvest yield, Tobit and stepwise regression analyses were employed for this purpose. Tobit regression was the primary analytical tool used to examine the data. Additionally,

stepwise regression was employed as a supplementary method to assess each influence factor (Wooldridge, 2009; Hutcheson, 2011; Stock et al., 2015; Siek et al., 2024).

The raw data was initially entered into Microsoft Excel for coding and grouping variables. Subsequently, the data was transferred to STATA for data cleaning, statistical analysis, and model development. Tobit and stepwise regression models were applied within STATA to identify key factors affecting market access and their influence on Long Coriander harvest yield. **Table 4** displayed cost of seed, total cost of other materials, cost of chemical fertilizer and biocide, cost of energy resource and water pump or engine, total land area (rai), seed rate per rai (kg), cultivated land area (rai), price per riel (kg), number of plants per year, transportation cost, number of harvests per year, and total cost of labors (excavation, plowing, and harvesting). The econometric results are visually detailed in the following tables and constructed models.

$$\ln Y_{harvest} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot \ln m7 + \beta_2 \cdot \ln m_{energyEng} + \beta_3 \cdot \ln m_{cheFerti} + \beta_4 \cdot \ln m_{othercost} + \beta_5 \cdot \ln labo1 + \beta_6 \cdot \ln labo2 + \beta_7 \cdot \ln labo3 + \beta_8 \cdot \ln Y_{Price} + \beta_9 \cdot \ln Cul_area + \beta_{10} \cdot \ln Cul_seed + \beta_{11} \cdot \ln Tota_land + \beta_{12} \cdot \ln Transpo + \beta_{13} \cdot \ln Y_NplanYear \quad (1)$$

Table 4. Logarithmic Variables, Acronyms, and Definitions

Variable	Definition
<i>lnm7</i>	Logarithm of Seed
<i>lnm_energyEng</i>	Logarithm Cost of Energy Resource & Water Pump/Engine
<i>lnm_cheFerti</i>	Logarithm Cost of Chemical Fertilizer & Biocide
<i>lnm_othercost</i>	Logarithm Cost of Other Materials (1-6)
<i>lnTranspo</i>	Logarithm of Transportation
<i>lnlabo1</i>	Logarithm of Labor of Excavation
<i>lnlabo2</i>	Logarithm of Labor of Plowing
<i>lnlabo3</i>	Logarithm of Labor of Harvesting
<i>lnY_Price</i>	Logarithm of Price Per Riel (Kg)
<i>lnCul_area</i>	Logarithm of Cultivated Land (Rai)
<i>lnCul_seed</i>	Logarithm of Seed Rate Per Rai (Kg)
<i>lnTota_land</i>	Logarithm of Total of Land (Rai)
<i>lnY_NplanYear</i>	Logarithm of Number of Plants Per Year
<i>lnY_havesYear</i>	Logarithm Number of Harvests Per Year

Results and Discussion

The study primarily used Tobit regression to assess how various factors influence the harvesting yield of Long Coriander, specifically focusing on their impact on market access. To further refine the analysis and determine the relative importance of each factor, stepwise regression was conducted as a secondary method. All numerical data was transformed into logarithmic values for analysis and indicated by the asterisk symbols that are placed following the values in the table. According to **Table 5**, the results of the logarithmic regression analysis of variables that influence the harvesting yield include the cost of energy resource and water pump or engine (*Inm_energyEng*), the cost of chemical fertilizer and biocide (*Inm_cheFerti*), and the cost of other materials (*Inm_othercost*) significantly impact market access on the harvesting yield at varying levels of significance (1%, 5%, and 10%), as demonstrated by both Tobit and stepwise regression analyses. The rising costs of electricity, gasoline, and other fuels directly increase operating expenses, strongly suggesting a significant impact on Long Coriander yield. The type of energy source and the pump or engine used substantially influence overall harvest output. Therefore, finding ways to conserve energy and reduce costs appears essential for producers.

Table 5. The Regression Results of Harvesting Yield as a Dependent Variable

Variable	Mean	Tobit Model			Stepwise Model		
		Coeff.	T-Value	P>T	Coeff.	T-Value	P>T
<i>lnm7</i>	13.13	0.233	1.66	0.195	0.213	1.84	0.125
<i>lnm_energyEng</i>	13.13	0.500**	3.24	0.048	0.578***	4.01	0.01
<i>lnm_cheFerti</i>	12.63	0.394*	2.68	0.075	0.442***	4.22	0.008
<i>lnm_othercost</i>	15.29	-0.175*	-2.35	0.101	-0.149*	-2.01	0.101
<i>lnTranspo</i>	8.31	0.762**	3.22	0.048	0.802**	3.61	0.015
<i>lnlabo1</i>	12.01	0.671**	4.25	0.024	0.707***	4.25	0.008
<i>lnlabo2</i>	11.76	-0.594**	-3.44	0.041	-0.646**	-3.72	0.014
<i>lnlabo3</i>	13.47	0.280*	1.81	0.167	0.336**	2.14	0.085
<i>lnY_Price</i>	8.13	-1.134**	-3.15	0.051	-1.261**	-3.39	0.019
<i>lnCul_area</i>	0.05	-0.512**	-2.57	0.082	-0.581**	-2.88	0.035
<i>lnCul_seed</i>	1.32	-0.732***	-5.93	0.01	-0.656***	-6.25	0.002
<i>lnTota_land</i>	1.30	0.039	0.79	0.485	-	-	-
<i>lnY_NplanYear</i>	0.94	0.139	1.41	0.253	-	-	-
<i>_cons</i>		-9.546	-1.91	0.152	-11.366	-2.52	0.053
<i>No.of obs.</i>		17			17		
<i>LR chi2(12)</i>		43.7100			41.1700		
<i>Prob> chi2</i>		0.0001			0.0000		
<i>Pseudo R2</i>		6.0272			5.6765		
<i>Log likelihood</i>		18.2300			16.9583		

Note: *10% Significance Level; **5% Significance Level; ***1% Significance Level

Likewise, the transportation variable (*lnTranspo*) also found significant impact, as the cost of transportation could impact market access and reduce profit margins, preventing producers from planting Long Coriander or making investments in production. Conversely, timely harvesting can be made quicker by effective transportation systems, which can also lower losses after harvest and potentially maximize total yield. The result can give producers access to a larger market and lead to higher prices, which will promote higher yields and better living conditions. The relevant significant variables (*lnlabo1*, *lnlabo2*, and *lnlabo3*) associated with labor costs, as well as the processes of soil preparation (excavation and plowing) and harvesting, significantly influence harvesting yield. High labor costs can result in premature harvesting, leading to lower yields and poorer quality. However, having sufficient labor expense planning also helps producers maximize output and minimize losses caused by labor shortages. Notably, Both Tobit and stepwise models suggest that the amount of cultivated land per rai (*lnCul_area*) and the price per kilogram of yield (*lnY_Price*) are statistically significant factors influencing harvesting yield at the 5% level. In these circumstances, the factors of cultivated land and price frequently impact harvest output in the agricultural sector. To effectively manage this agricultural production in alignment with government policies and market trends, producers must control unpredictable factors. These include the fact that cultivated land is rented, and market prices are heavily influenced by government policy shifts, technological advancements, and market demand. The final variable (*lnCul_seed*) represents the amount of seed needed to plant one rai of land (seed rate per rai, kg). Costs of seed discovered had the highest significance level of 1% in both Tobit and stepwise models compared to the rest. According to Long Coriander producers in Battambang, when the plant's seed shares raw materials or production processes,

a cost increase can become an influential factor on Long Coriander harvesting yield. When producers purchase these materials, prices increase due to supplier strategies (Eav & Darith, 2024).

Conclusions and Recommendations

Cambodian small-scale producers predominantly rely on traditional cultivating methods guided by experience and intuition rather than formal decision-making processes. Understanding the factors influencing harvest yield is essential for effectively developing the agricultural sector and improving economic sustainability. This study on Long Coriander cultivation in Battambang, Cambodia, revealed significant insights into the factors influencing harvesting yield and market access by employing Tobit and stepwise regression analyses to identify key variables impacting production. Moreover, it highlighted the importance of cultivated land and market price in influencing yield, emphasizing the need for producers to navigate external factors like land rental and government policies. Results indicated that costs including energy resources, water pumps or engines, chemical fertilizers and biocides, other materials, transportation, labors, cultivated land, and seed rate significantly influence harvesting yield. On top of that, the study investigated the crop's profitability and market demand; it also underscored the challenges faced by producers, such as fluctuating prices and labor constraints. Comprehending these elements is essential to refining farming methods, expanding market opportunities, and ensuring the long-term viability of Long Coriander cultivation in Cambodia. Based on the results, producers of Long Coriander would benefit from considering the following recommendations for the sake of gaining more knowledge into the factors influencing harvesting yield and access to the market:

- **Optimize resource allocation:** Given the significant impact of cultivated land, energy resources, and other inputs on yield, producers should carefully allocate resources. This involves conducting cost-benefit analyses to determine the optimal levels of investment in land, machinery, fertilizers, and labor. Additionally, exploring land-sharing or rental agreements could provide access to larger plots, potentially increasing overall yield and income.
- **Enhance market understanding and risk control:** Fluctuating prices pose a significant challenge. Producers should actively monitor market trends and consider strategies to mitigate price risks. This could include diversifying crops, exploring value-added products, or participating in producer cooperatives to collectively negotiate better prices. Furthermore, understanding market demand for different qualities of Long Coriander can help producers tailor their production accordingly.
- **Improve agricultural practices and knowledge:** Continuous learning and adoption of best practices are crucial for enhancing yield and productivity. Producers can benefit from attending agricultural extension programs, participating in farmer-to-farmer knowledge sharing, and experimenting with different cultivation techniques. Additionally, exploring the potential of organic farming or integrated pest management could reduce input costs and improve product quality.

Abbreviations

Approx.: Approximately

Kg: Kilogram

Rai: A unit of measurement of land area in Cambodia, equal to 1,600 square meters (approximately 0.40 acres)

Riels (KHR): The official currency of Cambodia

USD (US Dollar): The currency of the United States

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Conflict of Interests

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